

SITE SPHINX	DATE 28/VIII/80	AREA E-CHAPEL	SQUARE	PAGE
"Ledge Box" Feature No.	Coordinates:		Levels	
			Top:	Bottom:
	Filled Space DIMENSIONS			
Diameter:	Width: 26cm from large "set in" block to N lining slab	Length: 1.38 to vertical plug block w. end	Depth: 78 cm from stonework bottom to top of N lining slab.	

Locus	Mat.	Color	Hard.	Consis.	Pottery	Inclusions	
1	SAND-LIMESTONE DEBRIS	BUFF-GREY	loose	SAND: fine Limestone: Large frags to minute chips	T See storage	Lm ✓	Gp
					D ✓	Gr ✓ Chips	Char
						Do	
						Ba	
						Al	
Other	BLUE PAINTED LIMESTONE FRAGS, BLUE FRIT PARTICLES						
					T	Lm	Gp
					D	Gr	Char
						Do	
						Ba	
						Al	
Other							
					T	Lm	Gp
					D	Gr	Char
						Do	
						Ba	
						Al	
Other							
					T	Lm	Gp
					D	Gr	Char
						Do	
						Ba	
						Al	
Other							
					T	Lm	Gp
					D	Gr	Char
						Do	
						Ba	
						Al	
Other							

PHOTOGRAPH	Color: Roll/	No./	B&W: Roll/	No./
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DRAWN	Area Plan:	Feature Plan: 1:50 gen plan.	Sections: Section 25
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REMARKS; INTERPRETATION: The W roughly half of the ledge box was excavated by Lehn in 1978 - all pottery saved. Fill deemed ancient and undisturbed at that time. Salient feature of fill: small chips calcium carbonate w/ flat blue surface and pottery w/ blue pigment adhering. The dump of this clearing was left on floor of area between paws for about 1 year. When ARCE Sphinx Project began June 1979 the fill was replaced. The fill was taken out of the excavated portion of the box (re excavated) August 1980. It was noted there were many mud inclusions: bits of old newspaper, wire insulation, etc. Earlier it was realized that narrow E end of the ledge box rebuilt w/ mod. grey cement as mortar - prob. in 1926. In the loose sand fill spilling out of bottom of ledge box under projecting (floor?) slab there were also

noted mod. inclusions such as newspaper. It was assumed most of fill excavated in 1978 ancient, while fill underneath floor-like slab of box and some of interior fill toward E end may have been disturbed. As nothing modern noted in 1978 excavation at W end of fill, this may indeed be case. At any rate, when re-excavated fill sifted 28/VIII/80 a quantity of additional small calcium carbonate frags w/ blue pigment on a flat surface recovered. Also a good quantity of small granite fragments, small ceramic frags, and (of course by this time) mod inclusions (newspaper, wire insulation etc.).

ALSO: SOME PARTICLES BLUE FRIT EXCLUSIVELY.

3/IX/80: Abd al Laafi commences clearing remaining fill toward E half of ledge box. At outset, mod newspaper, straw protruding from standing section. But this, as became clear, a bit of refill from time we replaced fill taken out in summer 1978 (replaced June 1979). (See above). Remainder of fill seems clearly ancient, undisturbed. Hard packed, as much clay-like brown-dark brown, as sandy, and w/ many packed-in large sharp limestone frags. These frags measure from 20 cm across (largest) to very small fine chips.

More shards, including some w/ blue frit-like pigment adhering come up. Some irregular quartzite frags. Some rounded shaped quartzite frags. Smooth shiny chert-like pebble. Small granite chips. And many frags of blue coated calcium carbonate? Some at largest pieces of latter have a white matrix w/ blue adhering fine fibrous (hair) as though a kind of temper. [Wonder: could small quartzite rounded objects be tools for working glyphs? Do these and granite chips indicate ledge box built and filled roughly at time Thutmose IV stella erected and inscribed. Compare blue frit particles from feature 93 immediately above ledge box to bedrock jaw.]

At bottom of fill of 92 is rectangular limestone slab lying "loose" in fill.

E end of inside of ledge box looks to be blocked by ancient stone slab. Appears, therefore, mod limestone-cemented blocking at outside E end of box only is mod. patching. Had Laafi stop excavation, clean surface of fill for photo. A bit late for section of fill itself, although it is consistent to bottom and not stratified. (section left slopes down to loose rectangular slab at bottom to center of interior of feature.)

Also from undisturbed fill - 1 frag alabaster (5 x 5.5 x 6 cm) w/ 1 flat smooth (worked) face, 1 limestone chip (1 x 2.5 x 3.5) w/ black inked cross mark. Other marked smaller frags found.

3:00 PM Cut back fill at E end to a rough standing section. NOTE: A rough band of fine powdery red sand runs down S side of fill. Abd al Gadar cleared out the loose fill I had cut away. The claims in sifting this more mod Arabic newspaper (relatively old) came up - from specifically recess crack between flat laid flooring blocks at bottom and bedrock ledge. This is puzzling, because fill looks decidedly undisturbed - ancient w/ large frags at bottom and chips compacted in. The matrix is mottled sand pockets interspersed w/ dark brown sandy-dirt or clay. Could this damp discolored newspaper frag have infiltrated from below flooring blocks when loose sand spilling from under there to outside had mod. inclusions as noted before? Or contaminated during sifting operation? At any rate, these mod inclusions, w/ the history of our of the data.

4/IX/80 SECTION of remaining fill at E end drawn at 1:10. Seen that between bedrock of fine powdery red (paint?) sand. This designated ③. ② is compact fine sand between ledge and/or large in-set slab and ① Rubble fill. This shows in section drawing because ① here taken out. It is "behind" ① - RUBBLE FILL. Note how ③ and vertically placed rough heavy large chips against bedrock describe an intended contour of inner how could ③ be an earlier deposit than ① Rubble Fill as it would have fallen away if left or stripped bare. And no mortar bonds vertically set chips which show in ③. 10:30 I excavated most of remaining fill. ③ seems same, although tinted? deposit as ① because small blue frags and limestone chips run continuously from ① - ③. ② turns out to be compact mortar (set in earlier than ③) therefore? Nothing mod. noted in way of inclusions. My conclusion is fill undisturbed until 1978.

Abd al Laafi clears remainder of fill to interior E end of box.

③ - Fine red powdery sand and ① Rubble Fill sampled.

